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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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FIGHTING DRUG TRAFFICKING IN CENTRAL ASIA

ANNOTATION

The article examines the problem of drug trafficking in the Central Asian region. Drug trafficking from Afghanistan thus acts as a traditional threat to the states of Central Asia, which risk becoming an international center of drug trafficking and trafficking.

In the context of increasing areas under opium poppy cultivation in the southern provinces of Afghanistan, geographic proximity, the functioning of an extensive network of couriers, thriving corruption in the countries of the region and transparency of state borders, it can be said without exaggeration that the production of drugs in Afghanistan and their mass transportation to various parts of the mainland remains one of the main threats to stability and development prospects, which has already acquired the character of a national tragedy both for the countries of Central Asia and for the CIS member states and a number of EU countries.

Key words: drug trafficking, Afghanistan, organized crime groups, Central Asia, CIS, USA, UNODC, European Union, opium poppy, NATO.

МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ГИЁХВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРИНИ НОҚОНУНИЙ МУОМИЛАСИГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада Марказий Осиё минтақасида гиёхвандлик воситаларни ноқонуний савдоси муаммоси кўриб чиқилган. Афғонистондан гиёхвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний муомиласи ҳамда гиёхвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний савдосининг халқаро марказига айланиш хавфи остида турган Марказий Осиё давлатлари учун анъанавий таҳдид бўлиб келмоқда.

Афғонистоннинг жанубий вилоятларида кўкнори етиштириладиган майдонларнинг кўпайиши, географик жиҳатдан яқинлиги, кенг курерлар тармоғининг фаолият юритиши, минтақа мамлакатларида коррупциянинг авж олаётгани ва давлат чегараларининг шаффофлиги шароитида муболағасиз айтиш мумкинки, Афғонистонда гиёхвандлик воситаларни ишлаб чиқариш ва уларни материкнинг турли қисмларига оммавий ташиш барқарорлик ва ривожланиш истиқболларига таҳдид солувчи асосий таҳдидлардан бири бўлиб келмоқда, бу Марказий Осиё мамлакатлари учун ҳам, МДХга аъзо давлатлар ва бир қатор Европа Иттифоқи мамлакатлари давлатлари учун ҳам миллий фожиа характерини олмоқда.

Калит сўзлар: гиёхвандлик воситалар савдоси, Афғонистон, Бирлашган Миллатлар Ташкилотининг Наркотиклар ва жиноятчилик бўйича бошқармаси, уюшган жиноий гуруҳлар, Марказий Осиё, МДХ, АҚШ, Европа Иттифоқи, кўкнори, Шимолий Атлантика Шартномаси Ташкилоти.

БОРЬБА С НАРКОТРАФИКОМ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается проблема наркотрафика в центральноазиатском регионе. Наркотрафик из Афганистана выступает, таким образом, в качестве традиционной угрозы для государств Центральной Азии, которые рискуют стать международным центром наркоторговли и наркотрафика.

В условиях увеличения посевных площадей опийного мака в южных провинциях Афганистана, географической близости, функционирования разветвленной сети курьеров, процветающей коррупции в странах региона и прозрачности государственных границ, без преувеличения можно сказать, что производство наркотиков в Афганистане и их массовая транспортировка в различные районы материка остается одной из главных угроз для стабильности и перспектив развития, которая уже приобрела характер национальной трагедии как для стран Центральной Азии, так и для государств-участников СНГ и ряда стран ЕС.

Ключевые слова: наркотрафик, Афганистан, Управление Организации Объединенных Наций по наркотикам и преступности, ОПГ, Центральная Азия, СНГ, США, Европейский Союз, опиумный мак, Организация Североатлантического договора.

Afghanistan has been the world's largest producer of heroin and raw opium for several decades and thus determines the general trends of the world drug market. Over the past 14 years, this country has accounted for 90% of world opium production. This is 50% more than in the period before 2000. According to these indicators, Afghanistan has even surpassed Myanmar.

Until the mid-seventies of the last century, the use of opium poppy was carried out mainly for economic and industrial purposes. The use of opium as an intoxicant was strictly controlled at the community level. A small portion of the annual supply of Afghan opium was exported to Iran and Turkey.

It is inappropriate to talk about the presence of a drug market during this period of Afghan history. The situation changed in the 1970s, when a series of military-political events that occurred over the course of just one decade upset the delicate balance that had existed in Afghanistan since 1929.

The weakening of the power of Kabul, both in the center and locally, gave smugglers a free hand; peasants, whose arable areas had been reduced due to systematic bombing and shelling, were forced to turn to growing crops that were more profitable than Afghanistan's traditional cereals.

During this period, the production of narcotic substances becomes the main profitable activity, the money from which is used to purchase weapons, ammunition, food, and also to recruit mercenaries. Thus, in the 1970s–1980s. The foundations of the current drug trafficking infrastructure were laid at the junction of the eastern regions of Afghanistan and northwestern Pakistan.

After the withdrawal of Soviet troops on February 15, 1989, the outbreak of civil war finally undermined the already very weak economy, the basis of which was the agricultural sector, which was risky in the harsh climatic conditions of Afghanistan.

It was in the 1990s. Afghanistan became the main producer of opium poppy and a supplier of opium and heroin to the world market, but was not yet able to become an unconditional monopolist. Before the war of 1979–1989. opium poppy crops in Afghanistan were located mainly in Badakhshan and accounted for no more than 0.15% of the structure of sown areas.

Around the mid-1990s. The main opium poppy plantations in Afghanistan are in Helmand and Nangarhar, where up to three-quarters of all Afghan opium is produced. Since the Taliban came to power, active efforts to counter the cultivation of opium poppy have led to production falling to 185 tons per year.

However, after their overthrow by the Northern Alliance troops, drug production increased again. There was a surge in opiate production in the years following the US invasion of Afghanistan following the events of September 11, 2001.

The start of the “counter-terrorist” operation of the United States and Great Britain on the territory of Afghanistan on October 7, 2001, seemed to solve the problem of drug production in the country, but since the start of Operation Enduring Freedom, we have seen a qualitatively reverse trend.

Since September 11, 2001, drug production has quadrupled, as evidenced by data from various departments. It's no secret that during the years that ISAF troops were in Afghanistan, the country produced and exported more heroin than any other country in the world.

The Americans entered Afghan soil at a time when, in 2001, the country produced the smallest amount of opium raw material since 1992, only 185 tons, the cultivation of which covered less than 8 thousand hectares of territory. During the years of foreign invasion, drug production increased almost 40 times, reaching an unprecedented scale. ISAF has made the country under its control the sole leader among drug traffickers on the entire planet; 80% of the world's opium poppy harvest is harvested in Afghanistan.

Authorities in Afghanistan—both in Kabul and locally—continued from time to time to declare a certain degree of determination to stop the production of narcotic substances in the country. However, this determination was realized in measures of a predominantly demonstrative nature. If we look at the statistics published by official organizations, primarily UNODC, then in 2001, that is, the last year of Taliban rule in Afghanistan, opium production amounted to 185 tons.

This quantity was produced in the previous year and stockpiled by smugglers. In early 2001, Mullah Mohammad Omar issued a decree banning the cultivation of opium poppy. But how effective were the NATO group's measures to “fight” drug production?

After the invasion of US and NATO troops, drug production increased 40 times (from 2001 to 2014). According to data from the annual report of the UN Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), presented in Vienna, the amount of agricultural land in Afghanistan occupied by opium poppy crops has reached a record size of 328 thousand hectares, an increase of 63% over the year. “This level of opium poppy cultivation is a new record since systematic monitoring began (in 1994) and exceeded the previous record in 2014 by 104 thousand hectares, or 46%” [1].

2014 was to be a period of exceptional importance: the mandate of the International Security Assistance Force ended, followed by the withdrawal of the main contingent of NATO troops.

The international community had both great hopes for the establishment of political stability in the country and great fears due to the fact that the declared goals of the operation were not achieved by events. One of the important topics on the agenda was the question of drug production and drug trafficking, how the situation would change after the departure of NATO, because during the years that the Western Coalition troops were in Afghanistan, the flow of drugs did not fall, but rather increased.

In 2015, the potential volume of opium production in Afghanistan was 3,300 tons, thus production decreased by 48% compared to the previous year (in 2014 it was 6,400 tons). The decrease in volumes, according to experts, was mainly due to crop failure in the southern provinces of the country. However, Afghanistan – 183 thousand hectares – accounts for almost two-thirds of the global area of illicit opium poppy cultivation, which, by the way, in 2015 (compared to 2014) decreased by 11% to approximately 281 thousand hectares.

The sharp reduction in opium production in the main supplier of heroin on the world market - Afghanistan, by the way, did not lead to a reduction in the consumption of drugs in this group. It is possible to compensate for such fluctuations in production and maintain the supply of heroin at the same level by using up opium reserves accumulated over previous harvest years.

According to published data, opium production in the country increased in 2016 by 43% compared to 2015 and amounted to 4.8 thousand tons versus 3.3 thousand tons. The possibility of underestimating the harvest cannot be ruled out, since in carrying out calculations for a number of provinces oriented towards opium poppy cultivation, where the security situation is complex, average indicators of other provinces were used.

The dismal results of this season are explained by a number of factors. The area under opium poppy increased by 10% (201 thousand hectares in 2016 versus 183 thousand hectares in 2015). Thus, the province of Jawzjan, located in the north of the country, lost its “opium poppy-free” status, which it had had since 2008, and its area under opium poppy cultivation amounted to 409 hectares.

As you know, the Bureau of International Narcotics and Law Enforcement Affairs of the US State Department awards of up to \$1 million. provinces that have received or retained a similar status, which is assigned if opium poppy is cultivated on less than 100 hectares. Award recipients are determined based on poppy cultivation data from the annual Afghanistan Opium Survey. These funds are used to develop and implement development projects in the provinces. Currently, the drug crop is grown in 21 of the 34 provinces of Afghanistan [2].

The situation with measures to identify, prevent and eliminate crops containing narcotic plants continues to deteriorate, as government detachments encounter increasingly harsh resistance from the population, which sometimes even leads to the death of employees during operational and preventive operations.

This year, opium poppy eradication was carried out in only 7 Afghan provinces (12 in 2015), and only 355 hectares of area were eradicated, which is a more than 10-fold decrease compared to 2015 (3,760 hectares). But a more important factor was the high yield of opium poppy per hectare compared to previous years, amounting to 23.8 kg in 2016, which is 30% more than in 2015 - 18.3 kg. This was facilitated by more favorable weather conditions. conditions, as well as the absence of diseases and pests that previously often affected plants [3].

The leader in drug production in the country still remains the southern region (59%), where Helmand province alone accounts for almost 40% of the areas sown with poppy in Afghanistan. However, judging by the dynamics of production growth, the southern region, apparently, may soon give up its leading positions to the western and northern ones.

Particularly alarming is the explosive growth of drug production in the north of Afghanistan, directly bordering the Central Asian states. Thus, in the province of Badakhshan, neighboring Tajikistan, there is a constant increase in the area of cultivation of drug crops from 200 hectares in 2008 to 6298 hectares in 2016, i.e., almost 32 times in nine years.

In the Balkh province bordering Uzbekistan, which lost its “opium poppy-free” status only in 2015, the area under poppy cultivation immediately increased almost 10 times (to 2,085 hectares). But the greatest difficulties in 2017, apparently, await Turkmenistan, since drug traffickers have begun to develop the neighboring province of Jawzjan, and two other border provinces - Faryab (back in 2012, was free from opium poppy crops) and Badgiz - are striking in their pace growth of cultivated areas, amounting to 2,983 hectares (an increase of 152%) and 35,234 hectares (an increase of 184%) respectively [3].

Afghanistan occupies a leading position not only in the production of narcotic substances, but also in the export of opiates. Almost all international opiate smuggling routes originate from Afghanistan, a key global producer.

Direct routes for heroin smuggling from Afghanistan to consumer markets are not fixed and may change depending on the risk of detection of drug couriers. If earlier, before the victory of the Islamic Revolution in Iran in 1979, the traditional transport corridor was Afghanistan - Iran - Turkey - Southern Europe, then at the moment, post-Soviet countries are important links in the route of transporting heroin from production areas (the Golden Crescent) to consumers in developed countries Central Asia.

The northern route is one of the main heroin trafficking channels that connect Afghanistan with the huge markets of Russia and Western Europe. The proximity of the post-Soviet republics to Afghanistan with its rapidly developing drug business leads to the fact that the countries of this region themselves are being transformed from consuming countries into producing countries of narcotic substances. Evidence of this is the increasing frequency of operational reports from law enforcement agencies on the identification and arrest of one or another crime in the field of drug trafficking and production in different regions of the countries of the region.

The “Northern route” is commonly referred to as the export of Afghan opiates to Russia and Europe through Central Asia. It began to take shape in the early 1990s, immediately after the collapse of the USSR. After the withdrawal of Soviet troops from Afghanistan on February 15, 1989, the collapse of the USSR at the end of 1991 and the weakening of border controls, the “northern route” through the countries of Central Asia became the safest and cheapest.

According to data from the mid-1990s. The main routes for transporting drugs from Afghanistan through the CIS countries were approximately as follows:

- Afghan Badakhshan – Gorno Badakhshan – Osh – Sumgait, (Azerbaijan), processing;
- Bosnia, Croatia – Western Europe;
- Badakhshan – Osh – Volga region – Moscow – Estonia – Sweden;
- Badakhshan – Dushanbe – Bombory, Kobuleti (Georgia), processing – Adjara – Turkey;
- Mazar-i-Sharif – Termez – Samarkand – Ganja – Dagestan – Shali (ChR) – Moscow –

Siauliai;

Mazar-i-Sharif – Termez – Samarkand – Ganja – Dagestan – Karachay-Cherkessia – Abkhazia – Romania.

The situation in Tajikistan allowed drug traffickers to develop a route through Gorno-Badakhshan to the southern regions of Kyrgyzstan, which gradually turned into a transit corridor and transshipment base for transporting drugs to Central Asia and other CIS countries, as well as to Europe and the United States. International experts believe that the “Kyrgyz corridor” has become one of the six main drug trafficking routes from Afghanistan to the European market.

A common problem for many countries through which it passes is the ever-increasing volume of illegal transit and sale of Afghan drugs, the high rate of spread of drug addiction, HIV incidence and rising crime.

Data from the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) indicate that the activities of international organized crime groups (OCGs) to use the territory of Central Asian countries as a transit corridor for drugs of Afghan origin are intensifying.

This is also facilitated by the presence of developed cross-border and transcontinental land routes and air routes. Some of the drugs end up along the route, which leads to the involvement of the population of these countries in criminal activities related to drug trafficking.

According to experts, in 2016, the area of illegal opium poppy cultivation in Afghanistan compared to 2015 is estimated to have increased by 10%, to 201 thousand hectares. The growth of drug production in Afghanistan is directly related to the deteriorating military-political situation in this country.

Moreover, tension is growing near the territory of the Central Asian countries. And this creates conditions for criminal groups to organize their warehouses and laboratories near the border line. To date, drug trafficking from Afghanistan has intensified, and the number of drugs produced has increased. And there is also a higher level of traffic through the “northern route”.

In addition to negative social consequences, drug smuggling in Central Asia has led to the spread of corruption and the creation of shadow economies in these countries.

Such an economy includes activities such as mutually beneficial deals, uncertain work, economic activities outside government control, which are not reflected in official statistics, drug smuggling is also a type of such an economy due to the illegality of trafficking.

The shadow economy is outside the tax system and deprives the state of revenue. This, in turn, contributes to increasing economic problems in the countries of Central Asia. On the other hand, since drug trafficking is always considered a profitable trade, attracting investors to this trade prevents the development of legitimate investments in these countries.

This comes at a time when Central Asian countries are heavily dependent on investment to implement their economic projects, and investors are not interested in being present in economic activities in these countries due to the current tense situation. In other words, illegal investments are fighting against legal ones.

In addition, mafia groups receive large profits from drug smuggling for terrorist groups in this region, which leads to the strengthening of these groups, and as a result, contributes to an increase in military expenditures of the states of this region in connection with the fight against terrorist groups, which suppresses even before weak economies of these countries.

Thus, drug trafficking from Afghanistan through Central Asia is having an increasingly serious negative impact on the regional situation. It involves the broad masses, who are forced to engage in it due to poverty and lack of prospects, and women and youth are increasingly participating in the criminal business.

Over the more than twenty-year period of transit of Afghan opiates through the territory of Central Asian countries, they have registered a high level of drug addiction, HIV/AIDS incidence and drug-related crimes, which leads to social degradation of the population.

The shadow economy developing against this background impedes the development of legal industries, since there are no incentives for investment in the real economy.

To create optimal and safe conditions for the transit of drugs in the region, the drug mafia resorts to a proven method - bribery of officials, which leads to corruption of government and law enforcement agencies, which weakens the state.

The drug mafia is responsible for maintaining regional instability. It is interested in destabilizing the situation in the zone of its economic interests, i.e., where drug transit routes lie. The drug business in the countries of Central Asia is closely intertwined with extremist Islamist organizations and primarily the IMU [4].

The incursions of IMU militants into Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan in 1999–2000, the role of the drug business in the overthrow of power in Kyrgyzstan, in the events in the Rasht Valley of Tajikistan in 2010 and the riots in Zhanaozen in Kazakhstan in 2011 showed that the drug mafia has serious political ambitions. It seeks to control government power or at least significantly influence it.

In fact, the states of Central Asia spend a lot of money fighting these groups, which should be spent on the socio-economic development of the country and the well-being of their people. These drug cartels take advantage of vast opportunities and finances, and enhance their activities through large bribes to government authorities. The ranking of the international institute “Transparency International” on corruption in 100 countries of the world shows a high level of corruption among government officials in Central Asian countries [5].

This process contributes to the weakening of states and the superiority of private interests compared to public interests and leads to such consequences as a decrease in the capacity of government, the distance between the people and the elite, lack of confidence of the people in the government, radical actions on the part of the political opposition, isolation of youth groups and political figures. Undoubtedly, each of the mentioned consequences may impose large political and economic costs on the governments of these countries.

The rise of mafia drug activities also threatens tourism in these countries as the presence of mafia and opposition groups in any country prevents tourists from visiting these countries.

Taking into account the above, we can conclude that drug smuggling in Central Asia is a problem in the creation of which economic, political, social factors, as well as geographical conditions, play a role. Thus, a multi-pronged strategy will be needed to combat this problem.

Strengthening civil authorities, improving the economic situation, and introducing tough penalties for drug smugglers in the law can help resolve this problem. Otherwise, as the current situation continues, unemployed people will be more involved in the transit of drugs, which will contribute to increased unrest in the region.

There is no easy solution to the problem of drug trafficking from Afghanistan, whether we are talking about its impact on health or the shadow economy it creates. The Central Asian states will not be able to cope with the problem alone. Drug transit routes from production sites in Afghanistan to Russian and European consumers pass through them.

In general, Central Asian countries are limited in the funds they are able to allocate to combat drug trafficking, train personnel and maintain responsible policies. They must confront the geopolitical, which sometimes leads to a struggle between American and Russian projects and turns into arenas where the two powers measure their strength.

One way or another, these restrictions do not justify the erroneous assessments of external donors or the use of strategies based on myths propagated by the authorities of the Central Asian republics. These myths make the international community's efforts costly and largely futile.

Thus, the growth of geopolitical tensions and the ongoing crisis in Afghanistan contribute to the strengthening of existing threats and risks in the regional security system.

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